

Distribution of numbers of tillers 40 DAS in the F₂ of 3 crosses of upland varieties. ISRA, Senegal.

the theoretical level for 1 gene segregation (75–25%) gives a highly significant χ^2 .

In IRAT144/Abdoulaye Mano, environmental variance undoubtedly contributed to the continuous variation in the F₂ plants, which corresponds to

parental values. The weak expression of the tiller number character seems to influence moderate tiller numbers most. This explains why the residual heterosis was negative.

In the IRAT144/Barafita F₂, tiller

numbers at 40 DAS varied continuously. Data could not be used to test goodness of fit with expected segregation ratio. The distribution skewed more toward higher tiller numbers than it did in Barafita. □

Performance of ORS26-2014-4 (Lalat), a medium-duration variety

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ORS26-2014-4 (Obs 677/IR2071 //Bikram/ W1263), popularly called Lalat, is a 135-d variety. We compared it with 23 promising rice cultures of similar duration. The trial had 30-d-old seedlings transplanted 20 Feb 1986 at 20- × 15-cm spacing in 6.5-m² plots, in a randomized block design with 3 replications. Fertilizer was 80-40-40 kg NPK/ha. Pest infestation was measured at peak incidence.

Lalat performed best with a yield of 4.3 t/ha (see table). Its grain is medium bold with white kernel. The plant was 85.3 cm tall, flowered in 97 d, and produced 276 panicles/m². It was resistant to caseworm, leaffolder, and stem borer at heading. □

Yield performance and reactions to insect pests of 24 promising rice cultures. Chiplima, Sambalpur, India, 1986.

Culture	Plant ht (cm)	Days to 50% flowering	Panicles/m ²	Grain yield (t/ha)	Caseworm damage ^a	Leaffolder damage ^a (%)	Whitehead damage ^a (%)
ORI58-7-1	99.5	99	238.7	1.8	1.7	11.2	11.1
ORI96-2	74.7	99	345.0	2.1	0.7	7.5	7.5
OR131-5-8	84.0	92	292.0	1.2	0.3	15.3	15.3
NDU80	96.7	97	270.3	2.4	1.7	11.0	11.0
RP1570-6-5-4-1	88.8	95	211.0	1.5	0.3	13.3	13.3
KM6	78.0	88	257.7	1.8	0.7	15.7	15.1
UPR79-123	85.5	95	236.3	1.5	1.3	11.7	11.7
UPR103-44-2	81.3	101	232.3	1.7	4.3	12.5	12.5
OR268-408-5	87.8	110	202.7	1.2	1.3	8.9	8.8
NDR302	92.7	99	310.3	1.9	1.7	11.2	10.0
RP1570-44-1	87.3	95	306.0	2.3	0.3	13.2	13.2
RP1699-174-97-1	99.0	97	236.7	1.8	0.3	15.1	15.1
RP1699-183-133-1	97.2	106	326.0	1.3	0.3	11.0	11.2
RP1699-26-1-1	94.3	104	348.3	1.9	0.7	14.6	14.6
UPR231-28-1-2	80.3	91	290.3	2.5	1.3	11.7	11.7
RP2151-40-1	90.0	102	338.3	3.7	1.7	8.2	8.2
RP2151-21-22	96.5	103	295.0	3.0	0.7	5.8	5.8
RP1832-23-3-4	74.5	88	296.0	1.5	0.3	13.5	13.5
IR18348-36-3-3	89.3	92	255.3	2.4	0.7	10.7	10.7
Rasi	83.5	90	225.0	2.1	1.3	14.4	11.1
IR36	78.0	90	229.0	2.0	0.3	10.3	10.0
RP2240-153-1-51	79.0	92	215.7	2.1	0.7	14.6	14.5
ORS26-2014-4 (Lalat)	85.3	97	275.7	4.3	0.3	9.9	9.9
ORS26-2008	87.0	99	265.3	2.2	0.7	10.9	10.9

^a By the Standard evaluation system for rice.